

Sailing toward the final destination: SMAUG enters its final year of implementation!

Almost two years ago, in October 2023, the SMAUG project embarked on its journey with a clear mission: **to enhance and improve the security of ports and their entrance routes.** Over the last twenty-five months, we have continuously worked to overcome challenges, produce results, and enhance collaboration at both internal and external levels, fostering impactful synergies.

As we are heading to our final destination, our results are becoming tangible, and our objectives are steadily turning into measurable outcomes.

Embark on our journey to explore SMAUG's latest news and developments!

Port of Call: Latest News & Events

The SMAUG project has been actively showcasing its innovative research and work at key industry and academic events across Europe. From **major industry events to university demonstrations and General Assembly meetings**, explore the latest highlights and reflections from SMAUG's event participation.

SMAUG Discussions with our Experts

Through this series, our project partners offer their expert perspectives on core topics, including the CISE node, while also highlighting the project's aims, vision, and current status. Watch the videos below featuring [Hernando Reyes Martín](#), [Juan-Román Martínez Arranz](#) (INDRA), and Michael Codor (ATHANOR).

THE SMAUG PROJECT PRESENTS

Discussions with our experts

Hernando Reyes Martin, INDRA

THE SMAUG PROJECT PRESENTS

Discussions with our experts

Juan-Román Martínez Arranz, INDRA

Deep Dive into SMAUG

Join us as we take a deep dive into SMAUG's journey, **exploring key topics, technologies, and end-users'**

operations and requirements, to gain a comprehensive understanding of our technologies and work!

SMAUG End User's
Requirements

SMAUG Technologies
Validation

Maritime Security in Ports

Customs' Everyday Operations

SMAUG and UNDERSEC have joined forces!

SMAUG and **UNDERSEC**, two European projects funded through the Horizon Europe programme, are joining forces in a new strategic partnership. This collaboration aims to advance underwater security and resilience, enhancing protection for ships, ports, and critical maritime infrastructure across Europe.

[Learn more](#)

SMAUG Publications

From **Optimising Object Detection for Maritime Search and Rescue** to **AI, Data Governance and Cloud Cybersecurity in Maritime Surveillance**, the SMAUG publications cover research findings, technical developments, and operational use

cases that support the protection of ports, vessels, and critical maritime infrastructure.

Enjoy your read!

What's next?

The SMAUG project has successfully completed its first two years and is steadily progressing towards completion. The past two years were shaped by intense research, technical demonstrations, and achievements. The final year will focus on pilot tests, with continued impactful collaborations, participation in events, and more.

Stay tuned and join the SMAUG journey by following its social media profiles!

Funded by the
European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101121129. Views

and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

SMAUG

This email was sent to {{ contact.EMAIL }}
You've received this email because you've subscribed to our newsletter.

[Unsubscribe](#)

